

REMOTE REAL TIME CARDIAC ACTIVITY MONITORING USING IOT- BASED PLATFORM

1 Mrs. V. MOUNIKA, 2 A. BHANU SHREE, 3 G. INDU PRASHANTHI

4 B. MAHESH, 5 B. VARUN GOUD

1Assistant Professor, Department of CSE, Sri Indu College of Engineering and Technology-Hyderabad

2345Under Graduate, Department of CSE, Sri Indu College of Engineering and Technology-Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

In this article, a novel and an efficient methodology is presented for real-time monitoring of ECG signals. The method involves fast Fourier transform (FFT) based discrete wavelet transform (DWT) for extracting the features from the heartbeats which involves less computational complexity in terms of additions and multiplications operations for higher order filter lengths. These features extracted are recognized using particle swarm optimization (PSO) tuned twin support vector machines (TSVM) classifier. The TSVM classifier is four times faster than the standard SVM while the PSO technique is employed to gradually tune the classifier parameters to achieve more accuracy. The proposed methodology is implemented on IoT based microcontroller platform and validated on the benchmark Physionet data to classify 16 categories of ECG signals. Once an abnormality is detected, the platform generates a pop-up message as a warning and sends the information to a remote platform allowing hospitals to take preventive measures. The platform reported a higher overall accuracy of 95.68% than the existing studies. Further, such implementation can be utilized as a warning system in both homecare as well as tele-monitoring applications to continuously monitor the cardiac condition of a subject anywhere to the state-of-art heart disease diagnosis.

Keywords: **Cloud and Big Data, Data Security**

INTRODUCTION

Smart healthcare has emerged as a growing sector due to increased health awareness among consumers and rapid technological advancements. As a result, various advanced devices or gadgets are developed, those will serve an estimate of 808.9 million users by the end of 2020 to improve the healthcare technology

These devices are widely used to serve different purposes including but not limited to continuously monitor the biomedical signals like electrocardiography (ECG). These devices facilitate automatic efficient diagnosis of cardiac diseases by processing longer duration ECG recordings which is done by an experienced cardiologist and hence, they reduce the time required for analysis. These devices are developed considering the following key points like i) saving large quantity of biomedical data ii) developing devices having features offering low-energy consumption, higher computation capable, i.e., working at higher speed, battery operated, and long life iii) tele-medicine services using up-to-date smartphones based technology . Due to enhanced health care and increased patient compliance, usage of such devices have reported significant growth in the market. These devices/systems typically monitor the subject's condition which include blood pressure, essential indications and ECG.

As such, many new devices aiming to diagnose the cardiac diseases have evolved in market. Among those include (a) ECG monitoring system that provides cardiac activity of the subject, i.e., no storage of ECG data (b) event monitors that captures and record cardiac activity for lesser amount of time; (c) device that stores the condition of heart for longer period of time, i.e., the loop recorder, (d) telemetry solutions for ECG. In spite of these available solutions, the loss of life of patients are reported in many cases where the patient is unable to reach hospitals on time. The analysis of longer duration ECG records is time consuming, the cardiologists must depend on self- monitoring and symptom observed in subjects for their diagnosis. Therefore, it becomes necessary for the existing devices cardiac monitoring devices to deliver more features and must be smart rather than just storing the ECG. Currently, three possible ECG solutions reported. Among them include: 1) the solutions are used to store ECG signals only which is analyzed in off-line mode by a cardiologist. The devices such as Holters and Loop recorders typically stores the data only, i.e., no analysis is done, 2) the solutions performing real-time analysis from a remote place using servers such as mobi-health using personal development assistant (PDAs) or mobiles. These devices only send the data to the hospitals for processing allowing remote real-time monitoring, and 3) the solutions providing real-time evaluation within the device using updated smartphones to provide some intermediate level of diagnosis at the place of subject (point-of- care service). However, all these solutions manifest some limitations in analyzing ECG signals such as event-by-event evaluation is not conducted at the subject's place, patient is unknown about his cardiac status and has to be home bound. And the most important being the time required by the patient to get diagnosed from a nearest hospital upon an emergency. Several works have reported remote monitoring of ECG with the integration of wireless technology with the mobile devices/PDAs. The wireless technologies Include Bluetooth, wifi, RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) and ZigBee modules for enhancing the healthcare of a patient . The use of wireless technologies enables the development of a remote monitoring device targeting mass market. In , a Personal Digital Assistant (PDA) integrated with newly designed wireless sensor structure is reported to transmit ECG signal for monitoring with high flexibility. In a monitoring system consisting of ECG sensors, data acquisition system (DAQ), processing module, and a transceiver is presented which transfers the ECG signal using through Bluetooth to the server for analysis. In a wearable and wireless ECG system is designed using Bluetooth to detect 3-lead ECG signals using different algorithms where wavelet algorithm is reported as the most efficient. In a wireless monitoring system consisting of a WiFi module and Bluetooth is developed which transfers the physiological signals through Bluetooth to a server. In a monitoring system is designed using a video camera, an ECG transceiver where the data transferred is analyzed by physicians.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Internet of Things (IoT) technology has attracted much attention in recent years for its potential to alleviate the strain on healthcare systems caused by an aging population and a rise in chronic illness. Standardization is a key issue limiting progress in this area, and thus this paper proposes a standard model for application in future IoT healthcare systems. This survey paper then presents the state-of-the-art research relating to each area of the model, evaluating their strengths, weaknesses, and overall suitability for a wearable IoT healthcare system. Challenges that healthcare IoT faces including security, privacy, wearability, and low- power operation are presented, and recommendations are made for future research directions

The term health care has a very wide scope that ranges from lifestyle and wellness to care for acute conditions. With the availability of digital accessories for monitoring basic biological functions, the potential for obtaining detailed data on the lifestyle, habits, and behavior of an individual exists. Such data can enable the diagnosis of the causes for a condition with higher accuracy. Recently, a large number of devices have become available on the market that can monitor various aspects of lifestyle and biological functions. Such data provide feedback to an individual for compliance with healthy guidelines as well as contributing information to the health-care provider for use in the diagnosis of an ailment. In this article, we identify the various aspects of care that can benefit from consumer-grade health-monitoring devices and present the overall landscape in the context of self-care. We qualify the term consumer health care, assigning the context to it and identifying the services available in that context.

Wireless technology development has increased rapidly due to its convenience and cost effectiveness compared to wired applications, particularly considering the advantages offered by Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) based applications. Such applications exist in several domains including healthcare, medical, industrial and home

automation. In the present study, a home-based wireless ECG monitoring system using Zigbee technology is considered. Such systems can be useful for monitoring people in their own home as well as for periodic monitoring by physicians for appropriate healthcare, allowing people to live in their home for longer. Health monitoring systems can continuously monitor many physiological signals and offer further analysis and interpretation. The characteristics and drawbacks of these systems may affect the wearer's mobility during monitoring the vital signs. Real-time monitoring systems record, measure, and monitor the heart electrical activity while maintaining the consumer's comfort. Zigbee devices can offer low-power, small size, and a low-cost suitable solution for monitoring the ECG signal in the home, but such systems are often designed in isolation, with no consideration of existing home control networks and smart home solutions. The present study offers a state of the art review and then introduces the main concepts and contents of the wireless ECG monitoring systems. In addition, models of the ECG signal and the power consumption formulas are highlighted. Challenges and future perspectives are also reported. The paper concludes that such mass-market health monitoring systems will only be prevalent when implemented together with home environmental monitoring and control systems.

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

EXISTING SYSTEM

Currently, three possible ECG solutions reported. Among them include: 1) the solutions are used to store ECG signals only which is analyzed in off-line mode by a cardiologist. The devices such as Holters and Loop recorders typically stores the data only, i.e., no analysis is done, 2) the solutions performing real-time analysis from a remote place using servers such as mobi-health using personal development assistant (PDAs) or mobiles. These devices only send the data to the hospitals for processing allowing remote real-time monitoring, and 3) the solutions providing real-time evaluation within the device using updated smartphones to provide some intermediate level of diagnosis at the place of subject (point-of-care service). However, all these solutions manifest some limitations in analyzing ECG signals such as event-by-event evaluation is not conducted at the subject's place, patient is unknown about his cardiac status and has to be home bound. And the most important being the time required by the patient

to get diagnosed from a nearest hospital upon an emergency. Several works have reported remote monitoring of ECG with the integration of wireless technology with the mobile devices/PDAs. The wireless technologies include Bluetooth, WiFi, RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) and ZigBee modules for enhancing the healthcare of a patient. The use of wireless technologies enables the development of a remote monitoring device targeting mass market. In, a Personal Digital Assistant (PDA) integrated with newly designed wireless sensor structure is reported to transmit ECG signal for monitoring with high flexibility. In, a monitoring system consisting of ECG sensors, data acquisition system (DAQ), processing module, and a transceiver is presented which transfers the ECG signal using through Bluetooth to the server for analysis. In, a wearable and wireless ECG system is designed using Bluetooth to detect 3-lead ECG signals using different algorithms where wavelet algorithm is reported as the most efficient. In, a wireless monitoring system consisting of a WiFi module and Bluetooth is developed which transfers the physiological signals through Bluetooth server. In a monitoring system is designed using a video camera, an ECG transceiver where the data transferred is analyzed by physicians. In, the active RFID devices is employed through a mesh type multihop network extending the network area coverage, alongwith ZigBee modules between the hubs and the RFID readers for remote healthcare monitoring.

DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM

- Heart rate monitors or devices are not accurate.
- event-by-event evaluation is not conducted at the subject's place, Patient is unknown about his cardiac status.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

This study advances a step further considering the third type of solution. The basic idea of this study is to prototype a cardiac activity monitoring platform capable of allowing realtime diagnosis at the place of patient and integrated with the IoT technology. To perform automatic analysis and remote monitoring of ECG of a particular subject, an efficient signal processing and pattern recognition techniques are combined together and implemented on a suitable hardware platform. A discrete wavelet transform (DWT) method using fast Fourier transform (FFT) is employed for extracting vital characteristics from the pre-processed ECG signals. The use of FFT in standard DWT diminishes the computational burden significantly offering the implementation to be fast. These features extracted representing the heartbeats are applied as input to twin support vector machine (TSVM) algorithm for recognition into the sixteen categories. Here, the TSVM classifier performance parameters are optimized by implementing the particle swarm optimization (PSO) scheme. The proposed methodology is validated on the benchmark Physionet data and implemented on a microcontroller platform. The platform is evaluated under category oriented scheme to provide a generalized solution.

The input signals are generated in real-time and processed to identify sixteen classes of cardiac abnormalities. The categories of heartbeats identified by transmitter platform are transferred to a receiver platform using Wi-Fi unit interfaced with both the platforms.

The proposed methodology is faster and efficient than the conventional methods. The implementation can be considered as an extension of a hospital setup where a patient's ECG can be monitored remotely and thus, reduces the time required in delivering treatment to a subject remotely, thus enhancing the cardiac healthcare.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

- The proposed methodology is faster and efficient than the conventional methods.
- Reduce the time required in delivering treatment to a subject remotely, thus enhancing the cardiac healthcare.
- Heart rate monitors or devices are highly accurate.

IMPLEMENTATION

The major modules of the project are:

1. Patient
2. ECG Device
3. Server
4. Doctor

MODULES DESCRIPTION:

Patient :

This module consists of the patient's personal and medical records. Real-time data acquired by wearable sensors has been shown with respect to time. It contains the medical history of individual patient after getting registered at Android listening port device.

ECG Device:

Extracted physiological parameters give the alarming signals after comparison with assigned threshold values. These alarming signals indicate abnormalities like arrhythmia, hypotension, hypertension, fever, and hypothermia. Some real-time alarms from patients.

Server:

allows the involvement of multiple doctors in the web application for diagnosing patients. In case of large data from multiple patients, several doctors can get involved in monitoring and diagnosing processes. User management module can contain 100 users including doctors, patients, and nursing staffs for keeping record of patients.

Doctor:

After knowing about the abnormalities, the doctor can immediately track the current location of the patient which helps in both (1) reaching the patient and/or (2) sending ambulance to transfer the patient to hospital in case of serious emergency.

RESULTS

Abstract

In this article, a novel and an efficient methodology is presented for real-time monitoring of ECG signals. The method involves fast Fourier transform (FFT) based discrete wavelet transform (DWT) for extracting the features from the heart-beats which involves less computational complexity in terms of additions and multiplications operations for higher order filter lengths. These features extracted are recognized using particle swarm optimization (PSO) tuned twin support vector machines (TSVM) classifier. The TSVM classifier is four times faster than the standard SVM while the PSO technique is employed to gradually tune the classifier parameters to achieve more accuracy. The proposed methodology is implemented on IoT based micro-controller platform and validated on the benchmark Physionet data to classify 16 categories of ECG signals. Once an abnormality is detected, the platform generates a pop-up message as a warning and sends the information to a remote platform allowing hospitals to take preventive measures. The platform reported a higher overall accuracy of 95.68% than the existing studies. Further, such implementation can be utilized as a warning system in both home care as well as tele-monitoring applications to continuously monitor the cardiac

HOME SCREEN

Patient Login

UserName	<input type="text"/>
Password	<input type="password"/>

PATIENT LOGIN SCREEN

ADD CARDIAC DETAILS

In add cardiac details screen we have to add the cardiac condition of the patient .and this details are saved in the application for checkup purpose.

AN EFFICIENT
IoT-Based Platform for Remote Real-Time
Cardiac Activity Monitoring

Home View Profile **Add Cardiac Details** View Response Logout

ADD CARDIAC DETAILS....!!!

Select Condition

HeartBeat

Submit

CONCLUSION

This chapter presents an Internet-of-Things (IoT) based embedded platform to monitor and analyze the electrocardiography (ECG) of cardiac outpatients for improving the healthcare, i.e., smart healthcare. An improved version of discrete Wavelet transform (DWT) is implemented using FFT that extracts the important time-frequency features from corresponding ECG signals of patients. These features are classified using particle swarm optimization (PSO) based twin support vector machine (TSVM) classification scheme. The PSO technique determine the optimal classifier parameters to achieve the best classification accuracy. The proposed method has significant advantage of computational complexity over conventional DWT and SVM methods. The scheme is prototyped on a microcontroller platform to facilitate real-time processing and validated on the physionet data. The platform is interfaced with the Wi-Fi module to send the classified outputs to receiver platform. The platform reported an accuracy of 95.58% which can be considered as efficient in arrhythmia detection.

FUTURE SCOPE

The goal of this IoT system is to improve the medical care service to people at potential risk for heart incidents located at remote places by providing a monitoring system that helps doctors in the patient's heart signal supervision. Besides, authorized people can supervise patients accessing their ECG via the web.

REFERENCES

- [1]S. B. Baker, W. Xiang, and I. Atkinson, —Internet of Things for smart healthcare: Technologies, challenges, and opportunities,|| IEEE Access, vol. 5, pp. 26521–26544, 2017.
- [2]G. K. Garge, C. Balakrishna, and S. K. Datta, —Consumer health care: Current trends in consumer health monitoring,|| IEEE Consum. Electron. Mag., vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 38– 46, Jan. 2018.

- [3]N. Dey, A. S. Ashour, F. Shi, S. J. Fong, and R. S. Sherratt, —Developing residential wireless sensor networks for ECG healthcare monitoring,|| IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron., vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 442–449, Nov. 2017.
- [4]S. Raj and K. C. Ray, —A personalized point-of-care platform for realtime ECG monitoring,|| IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron., vol. 66, no. 4, pp. 452–460, Dec. 2018.
- [5]S. Raj, —An efficient method for computer-aided diagnosis of cardiac arrhythmias,|| in Machine Learning With Health Care Perspective (Learning and Analytics in Intelligent Systems), vol. 13, V. Jain and J. Chatterjee, Eds. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, Mar. 2020, pp. 295–315.
- [6]C. H. Hung, Y.-W. Bai, and R.-Y. Tsai, —Design of blood pressure measurement with a health management system for the aged,|| IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron., vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 619–625, May 2012.
- [7]M. Neyja, S. Mumtaz, K. Huq, S. Busari, J. Rodriguez, and Z. Zhou, —An IoT-based e-Health monitoring system using ECG signal,|| in Proc. IEEE Glob. Commun. Conf. (Globecom), Dec. 2017, pp. 1–
- [8]L. H. Wang, T. Chen, K.-H. Lin, Q. Fang, and S.-Y. Lee, —Implementation of a wireless ECG acquisition SoC for IEEE 802.15.4 (ZigBee) applications,|| IEEE J. Biomed. Health Informat., vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 247–255, Jan. 2015.